

D3.2 European Citizen Science Academy technology training products

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List of definitions and acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CS	Citizen science
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSDA	Citizen Science Data Academy
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form (European Commission 2016).
EC	European Commission
ECS	European Citizen Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The “Data Analysis and Visualisation Learning Path” is Deliverable 3.2 (D3.2) from the EU-funded project European Citizen Science (ECS). This deliverable is part of WP3 ‘Citizen Science Data Academy Technical Building’, which has the overarching objective of establishing the Citizen Science Data Academy (CSDA). The CSDA aims to enhance data literacy among citizen scientists by providing structured training and resources.

This deliverable focuses on the development and launch of the “Data Analysis and Visualisation” learning path, comprising a series of courses designed to equip citizen scientists with essential skills in data manipulation, analysis, and visualisation. The courses included are Introduction to Jupyter Notebooks, Introduction to Python, Introduction to NumPy, Introduction to Pandas, and Data Visualisation in Python. The primary objective of this document is to present a comprehensive overview of the newly developed courses, highlighting their relevance and importance to the citizen science community. These courses are intended to address the technological gap that often hinders effective participation in citizen science projects, thereby empowering participants to contribute more meaningfully to scientific research.

The document is structured as follows:

Section 1 provides an introduction, including an overview of the ECS project, the importance of the CSDA, and the specific objectives of Deliverable 3.2. It sets the stage for understanding the context and significance of the learning path.

Section 2 describes the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path in detail, outlining its objectives and the critical role it plays in enhancing

data literacy within the citizen science community. This section explains how the learning path addresses existing technological gaps and prepares participants for advanced data-driven research.

Section 3 delves into each of the five courses, providing detailed descriptions and key learning outcomes. It emphasises the practical skills and knowledge that participants will gain, enabling them to handle and interpret data effectively.

Section 4 explores the integration of Jupyter Notebooks into the courses. It highlights the benefits of using Jupyter Notebooks, the technical implementation within the courses, and the enhanced user interaction and practical application that this integration facilitates.

Section 5 justifies the inclusion of the data analysis and visualisation courses in the CSDA. It explains their relevance to citizen science projects, emphasising how these skills are crucial for data literacy, practical applications, and case studies that demonstrate their impact on real-world research.

Section 6 outlines the future steps for refining the courses based on participant feedback, expanding connections with real databases, and establishing an open call for citizen science projects.

The successful launch of the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path is a significant achievement for the ECS project. By providing citizen scientists with the tools and knowledge needed to analyse and visualise data, we enhance their ability to contribute to scientific research and foster a more inclusive and collaborative approach to science. This deliverable marks the beginning of a continuous journey towards empowering the citizen science community with essential data literacy skills.

1. Introduction

1.1. Overview of the European Citizen Science (ECS) Project

The overall objective of ECS is to widen and strengthen the European Citizen Science community through capacity-building and awareness-raising activities, such as the creation of a European Citizen Science Academy and the establishment of a network of 28 ECS Ambassadors. ECS will capitalise on EU-funded actions such as the [eu-citizen.science platform](#) to support links and collaboration between members of the European Citizen Science community, who will be involved in the co-design and co-creation of a large variety of services, strategic priorities, training opportunities and policy recommendations. A key focus is on inclusivity, which will be achieved through dedicated actions such as engaging libraries affiliated to the Public Libraries 2030 network to attract underrepresented publics, as well as ad-hoc support to countries/regions lacking citizen science networks, platforms and policy recognition.

ECS will create extensive capacity-building opportunities by engaging in particular excellent researchers in a variety of disciplines, for example, through the involvement of the Marie Curie Alumni Association, and emerging Horizon Europe Missions, Clusters, and wider ERA activities, to allow easy access for newcomers in citizen science activities. ECS is committed to push modern science towards open science as its modus operandi by providing open collaborative spaces where citizen scientists can familiarise themselves with the concept of "open and FAIR data with open and FAIR tools" and get actively engaged, while connecting with existing e-infrastructures such as EOSC through the collaborative development of data/metadata services. The engagement of the Citizen Science Global Partnership will guarantee wide international cooperation. These efforts will result in a number of key scientific, societal and policy impacts that will strongly contribute to securing Europe's global position as a leader in citizen science throughout the entire research and innovation system.

The six specific objectives of ECS are:

- **Objective 1:** Empower the European citizen science community through co-design and co-creation.
- **Objective 2:** Strengthen the links and collaboration between existing citizen science initiatives.
- **Objective 3:** Increase the participation of citizens from all walks of life in citizen science through an inclusive approach.
- **Objective 4:** Build the capacity to conduct excellent research and innovation through citizen science.
- **Objective 5:** Raise awareness, support and mainstream citizen science among new actors, new territories and scientific fields.
- **Objective 6:** Better align data infrastructures to the needs of citizen science, and improve open science practices employed by citizen science initiatives.

1.2. Importance of the Citizen Science Data Academy (CSDA)

The Citizen Science Data Academy (CSDA) is a pivotal component of the ECS Project. It serves as an educational hub designed to equip citizen scientists with the necessary skills to manage, analyse, and visualise data effectively. The CSDA aims to address the growing need for data literacy among citizen scientists, enabling them to contribute more meaningfully to research projects and enhance the overall quality of scientific outputs.

By providing structured training and resources, the CSDA empowers participants to harness the full potential of data in their citizen science initiatives.

1.3. *Objective of Deliverable 3.2*

Deliverable 3.2, titled “European Citizen Science Academy technology training products,” marks a significant milestone in the ECS Project. This deliverable encompasses the development and launch of a comprehensive learning path focused on data analysis and visualisation. The primary objective is to provide citizen scientists with the foundational skills required to analyse and interpret data, thereby enhancing their contributions to scientific research. This document outlines the structure, content, and significance of the newly developed courses, which are designed to address the technological gaps within the citizen science community and promote effective data-driven research practices.

In the following sections, we will delve into the details of the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path, explore the individual courses, and highlight their relevance to citizen science projects. Additionally, we will discuss the integration of Jupyter Notebooks, future steps for course refinement, and the planned open call for citizen science projects to contribute real-world datasets. This comprehensive overview will provide a clear understanding of the efforts undertaken to build the Citizen Science Data Academy and its impact on the broader ECS Project.

2. The ‘Data Analysis and Visualisation’ learning path

2.1. *Description and objectives*

As part of the ECS Academy, the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path is a carefully curated series of courses aimed at equipping citizen scientists with the essential skills needed for data manipulation, analysis, and visualisation. This learning path encompasses a sequence of 5 interconnected courses designed to build upon each other, ensuring a comprehensive and structured approach to mastering these crucial aspects of data science.

The primary objectives of this learning path are to:

- Provide a foundational understanding of data analysis and visualisation techniques.
- Enable participants to handle, process, and analyse data efficiently.
- Equip learners with the skills to create insightful and effective visualisations.
- Foster a deeper understanding of the tools and methodologies used in data science.

By the end of this learning path, participants will have developed the competencies necessary to contribute meaningfully to citizen science projects, leveraging data to drive scientific discovery and public engagement.

2.2. Importance for the citizen science community

In the context of citizen science, the ability to analyse and visualise data is of paramount importance. Citizen scientists often gather vast amounts of data from various sources, including environmental sensors, surveys, and public records. However, without the skills to effectively process and interpret this data, much of its potential value remains untapped.

The Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path addresses this critical need by providing citizen scientists with the knowledge and tools to transform raw data into meaningful insights. This capability not only enhances the quality and impact of citizen science projects but also empowers participants to engage more deeply with scientific research.

By democratising access to data science education, this learning path helps bridge the gap between professional scientists and the public, fostering a more collaborative and inclusive approach to scientific inquiry. As a result, the citizen science community becomes better equipped to tackle complex research questions, contribute to scientific advancements, and drive positive societal change.

2.3. Addressing the technological gap

The citizen science community often faces a significant technological gap, particularly in the realm of data analysis and visualisation. Many participants lack formal training in these areas, which can hinder their ability to contribute effectively to research projects. The Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path is designed to address this gap by providing targeted, accessible training that meets the specific needs of citizen scientists.

The courses within this learning path cover a range of essential topics, from the basics of programming in Python to advanced techniques for data manipulation and visualisation. By breaking down complex concepts into manageable lessons, the learning path ensures that participants can progressively build their skills and confidence.

Moreover, the integration of Jupyter Notebooks throughout the courses provides a hands-on, interactive learning experience. This approach allows learners to apply theoretical knowledge in practical scenarios, reinforcing their understanding and enabling them to tackle real-world data challenges.

3. Course details

The Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path comprises five distinct courses, each meticulously designed to build upon the previous one, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of data science concepts and techniques. Here we provide detailed descriptions and key learning outcomes for each course.

3.1. Introduction to Jupyter Notebooks

Course description: The “Introduction to Jupyter Notebooks” course is a foundational course that introduces learners to the powerful interactive computing environment provided by Jupyter Notebooks. This course covers the basics of using Jupyter Notebooks, including how to navigate the interface, create and manage notebooks, and execute code cells.

Key learning outcomes:

- Understand the core features and benefits of Jupyter Notebooks.
- Navigate the Jupyter Notebook interface with ease.
- Create, edit, and run code cells within a notebook.
- Utilise Markdown cells for documentation and notes.

3.2. Introduction to Python

Course description: The “Introduction to Python” course offers a thorough overview of Python programming, encompassing fundamental concepts and syntax. It is tailored specifically for complete beginners in programming and aims to establish a strong foundation in Python. This prepares students to tackle more advanced subjects in data analysis and visualisation.

Key learning outcomes:

- Grasp the basic syntax and structure of Python.
- Define and manipulate variables.
- Perform arithmetic operations and basic calculations.
- Understand and use data structures such as lists, tuples, and dictionaries.
- Understand the potential of functions in programming.
- Build algorithms using conditional statements and loops.

3.3. Introduction to NumPy

Course description: The “Introduction to NumPy” course delves into NumPy, a fundamental library for numerical computing in Python. This course covers the creation and manipulation of NumPy arrays, which are essential for efficient data analysis and scientific computing.

Key learning outcomes:

- Install and import NumPy.
- Understand the basics of NumPy arrays and their advantages over Python lists.
- Create and manipulate one-dimensional and multi-dimensional arrays.
- Perform basic operations and mathematical functions on arrays.
- Utilise NumPy for efficient numerical computations.

3.4. Introduction to Pandas

Course description: The “Introduction to Pandas” course provides an in-depth look at Pandas, a powerful library for data manipulation and analysis in Python. This course focuses on the foundational elements of Pandas, including series and dataframes, and covers techniques for indexing, selecting, and assigning data.

Key learning outcomes:

- Understand the basics of Pandas series and dataframes.

- Create and manipulate series and dataframes for data analysis.
- Efficiently index, select, and assign data within dataframes.
- Handle missing data and perform data summarization.
- Apply grouping, merging, and concatenation techniques for advanced data manipulation.

3.5. Data visualisation in Python

Course description: The “Data visualisation in Python” course explores various libraries and techniques for creating visual representations of data in Python. This course covers the use of Matplotlib, GGPlot, Seaborn, and Bokeh, providing learners with the skills to create both static and interactive visualisations.

Key learning outcomes:

- Install and import Matplotlib, GGPlot, Seaborn, and Bokeh.
- Create basic plots such as line, bar, and scatter plots using Matplotlib.
- Understand and apply the grammar of graphics in GGPlot for complex visualisations.
- Generate statistical plots like histograms and box plots using Seaborn.
- Develop interactive and web-ready visualisations with Bokeh.
- Customise and enhance visualisations for effective data representation.

Each course in the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path is designed to be engaging and informative, providing learners with the essential tools and knowledge needed to succeed in the field of data science. By the end of this learning path, participants will be well-equipped to handle a wide range of data analysis and visualisation tasks, enhancing their contributions to citizen science projects and beyond.

4. Integration with Jupyter Notebooks

The integration of Jupyter Notebooks into the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path provides a dynamic and interactive learning experience. This section elaborates on the benefits of using Jupyter Notebooks, the technical implementation within the courses, and the enhanced user interaction and practical application that this integration facilitates.

4.1. Benefits of using Jupyter Notebooks

Jupyter Notebooks offer numerous advantages that make them an ideal tool for teaching data analysis and visualisation:

- **Interactive learning environment:** Jupyter Notebooks allow learners to write and execute code in a step-by-step manner. This interactive approach helps reinforce concepts as students can immediately see the results of their code.
- **Integrated documentation:** The ability to combine code with rich text elements such as headings, explanations, and links makes Jupyter Notebooks a comprehensive learning tool. Learners can write notes and document their work within the same environment.

- **Visual representation:** Jupyter Notebooks support the inclusion of visualisations directly within the notebook. This capability is essential for data analysis and visualisation courses, as it allows students to create and view plots alongside their code.
- **Accessibility:** Jupyter Notebooks can be accessed from any device with an internet connection, making them a versatile tool for remote learning. The notebooks can be shared easily, promoting collaboration and peer learning.
- **Real-Time feedback:** Instant feedback on code execution helps learners identify and correct errors quickly, enhancing the learning process and making it more efficient.

4.2. Technical implementation in the courses

The integration of Jupyter Notebooks within the courses involves several key technical components to ensure a seamless and effective learning experience:

- **Pre-configured Notebooks:** Each course comes with pre-configured Jupyter Notebooks that include all necessary libraries and dependencies. This setup ensures that learners can focus on the content without worrying about installation issues.
- **Interactive code cells:** The notebooks are designed with interactive code cells that allow learners to write and execute code directly within the notebook. Each exercise and example is followed by code cells where students can practise and experiment with the concepts being taught.
- **Embedded visualisations:** The courses include embedded visualisations using libraries such as Matplotlib, Seaborn, and Bokeh. These visualisations are integrated into the notebooks to provide real-time visual feedback on the data analysis and visualisation tasks.
- **Step-by-Step instructions:** Detailed, step-by-step instructions are provided within the notebooks to guide learners through the exercises. These instructions help students understand the process and reasoning behind each step, making the learning experience more intuitive.
- **Self-contained environment:** Jupyter Notebooks used in the courses are hosted on JupyterHub, providing a self-contained environment where learners can work on their notebooks without the need for local installations. This setup also ensures that all students have a consistent learning environment.

4.3. User interaction and practical application

The integration of Jupyter Notebooks significantly enhances user interaction and the practical application of knowledge:

- **Hands-on practice:** By working directly within the Jupyter Notebooks, learners can apply theoretical knowledge to practical exercises immediately. This hands-on approach helps solidify understanding and improves retention.
- **Problem-solving skills:** The interactive nature of Jupyter Notebooks encourages learners to experiment with code and solve problems independently. This practice develops critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are crucial for data analysis.
- **Real-world scenarios:** The notebooks include exercises that mimic real-world data analysis scenarios. Learners work with actual datasets and face challenges that they are likely to encounter in professional or research settings. This practical experience prepares them for real-world applications of their skills.
- **Immediate feedback:** The ability to execute code and see results instantly provides learners with immediate feedback. This feature helps them understand the impact of their code and make necessary adjustments on the fly.
- **Collaboration and sharing:** Jupyter Notebooks can be easily shared and collaborated on, fostering a collaborative learning environment. Students can work on group projects, share insights, and learn from each other's experiences.

The integration of Jupyter Notebooks into the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path offers a robust, interactive, and practical approach to learning. By combining theoretical knowledge with hands-on practice and real-time feedback, Jupyter Notebooks enhance the overall learning experience, making it more engaging and effective. This integration not only equips learners with the necessary skills but also prepares them to apply these skills in real-world scenarios, thereby bridging the gap between education and practical application.

5. Relevance to CS projects

Including the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path within the ECS Academy may not initially seem to align directly with traditional notions of citizen science. However, the skills and knowledge imparted through these courses are critically important to the citizen science community. This section explores the relevance of these courses to citizen science projects and highlights the importance of their inclusion in the ECS Academy by highlighting their substantial impact on enhancing data literacy, practical applications in citizen science, and the potential for case studies and use cases.

5.1. Enhancing data literacy

Data literacy is the ability to read, understand, create, and communicate data as information. In the context of citizen science, data literacy is essential for participants to effectively engage in research projects, analyse findings, and contribute valuable insights. The Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path provides citizen scientists with the foundational skills needed to handle and interpret data confidently.

- **Empowering participants:** By learning how to manipulate, analyse, and visualise data, citizen scientists become more empowered to take an active role in research projects. They can move beyond merely collecting data to understanding and interpreting it, leading to more meaningful contributions.
- **Quality and accuracy:** Enhanced data literacy leads to improved data quality and accuracy. When citizen scientists understand the principles of data analysis, they can identify and correct errors, apply appropriate methods, and ensure that their findings are reliable and robust.
- **Effective communication:** Data visualisation skills enable citizen scientists to communicate their findings more effectively. Clear and compelling visualisations make it easier to share results with the broader community, including stakeholders, researchers, and the general public.

5.2. Practical applications in citizen science

The skills taught in the Data Analysis and Visualisation courses have direct applications in a wide range of citizen science projects. Whether participants are involved in environmental monitoring, biodiversity surveys, public health studies, or social science research, the ability to analyse and visualise data is invaluable. Some examples of application in fields in which citizen science works on a regular basis:

- **Environmental monitoring:** Citizen scientists engaged in monitoring air or water quality, tracking wildlife populations, or studying ecological changes can use data analysis techniques to identify trends, anomalies, and patterns in their data. Visualisation tools can help present these findings in an accessible and understandable manner.
- **Public health studies:** In projects related to public health, such as tracking disease outbreaks or assessing community health metrics, data analysis and visualisation are crucial. Participants can use

these skills to analyse health data, identify risk factors, and communicate findings to health authorities and the public.

- **Social science research:** Not only in projects that generate eminently numerical data, but projects that involve collecting survey data, studying community behaviours, or assessing social interventions benefit greatly from data analysis and visualisation. These skills enable citizen scientists to process large datasets, uncover insights, and share their findings with policymakers and community leaders.

In summary, the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path is highly relevant to the citizen science community. By enhancing data literacy, providing practical skills for data analysis and visualisation, and illustrating their application through case studies and use cases, these courses empower citizen scientists to make more meaningful contributions to research projects. The inclusion of this learning path in the ECS Academy is justified by its potential to bridge the technological gap and promote a more data-driven approach to citizen science.

6. Next steps

The successful launch of the Data Analysis and Visualisation learning path marks a significant milestone in the ECS Academy. However, the journey does not end here. Continuous improvement, expansion, and engagement with the community are essential to ensure that these courses remain relevant and impactful. This section outlines the future steps we will take to refine the courses based on feedback, expand connections with real databases, and establish an open call for citizen science projects.

6.1. Refinement of courses based on feedback

To ensure that the courses meet the evolving needs of the citizen science community, we will undertake a systematic approach to gather and incorporate feedback:

- **Pilot testing:** Before rolling out major updates, we will conduct pilot tests with a small group of participants to validate the courses and ensure they meet the desired objectives. This iterative process will help refine the courses further and ensure they deliver maximum value.
- **Feedback collection:** We will implement mechanisms for collecting feedback from participants after each course. This may include surveys, feedback forms, and direct communication channels to capture their experiences, suggestions, and areas for improvement.
- **Analysis and iteration:** The feedback collected will be analysed to identify common themes and specific areas that need enhancement. Based on this analysis, we will iterate on the course content, structure, and delivery methods to address gaps and improve the overall learning experience.

6.2. Expanding connections with real databases

To enhance the practical application of the skills taught in the courses, we aim to establish stronger connections with real-world databases and data sources:

- **Partnerships with data providers:** We will seek partnerships with organisations and projects that can provide access to relevant datasets. These partnerships will enable us to integrate real-world data into the course exercises, making the learning experience more authentic and applicable.

- **Curated data repositories:** We plan to review repositories of datasets specifically selected for their relevance to citizen science projects (EOSC, Zenodo...). Course participants will be able to access these repositories, which will provide valuable resources for practice and project work.
- **Regular updates:** As new data becomes available, we will update the course materials to include these datasets. This ongoing effort will ensure that the courses remain current and aligned with the latest trends and developments in the field of citizen science.

6.3. Open Call for citizen science projects

To foster greater community engagement and collaboration, we will establish an open call for citizen science projects to contribute their data and participate in the ECS Academy:

- **Objective and process:** The open call will invite citizen science projects to submit their datasets and propose challenges that can be addressed using the skills taught in the courses. We will provide guidelines and support to help projects prepare their data for integration into the learning path.
- **Community involvement:** By involving the community in this process, we aim to create a dynamic and collaborative environment where citizen scientists can learn from each other's experiences and contribute to each other's success. This initiative will also help highlight the diverse range of projects and research being conducted within the citizen science community.
- **Expected outcomes:** The open call is expected to result in a rich collection of real-world datasets and challenges that enhance the practical relevance of the courses. Participants will have the opportunity to work on meaningful projects, apply their skills to solve real-world problems, and contribute to the advancement of citizen science.

In conclusion, the future steps outlined here represent a commitment to ongoing improvement, community engagement, and innovation. By refining the courses, expanding connections with real-world data, and fostering collaboration through open calls, we will continue to enhance the value and impact of the ECS Academy. Our ultimate goal is to empower citizen scientists with the skills and knowledge they need to drive scientific discovery and societal change.